

PAREMIOLOGY: A NATURAL BRIDGE BETWEEN DIFFERENT HERITAGES

Rui Soares (AIP-IAP);

Marinela Soares (AIP-IAP)

Email: runo_mari@yahoo.com;

neli_rui@hotmail.com

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This communication, integrated into the topic "*Training and Pedagogy: Teaching strategies for multiprofessional, multilingual team collaboration*", aims at the implementation of a seminar entitled PAREMIOLOGY: A NATURAL BRIDGE BETWEEN DIFFERENT HERITAGES, hereinafter referred to as P:PNEDP. As the seminar title suggests, the proposal presented constitutes a challenge to the application of the educational potential of proverbs and related expressions, directed at teams with different levels of responsibility in the transmission of values. In an era where migratory phenomena are a global reality with global consequences, it is urgent to sensitize the various stakeholders in the process of welcoming migrants into society to "*think globally and act locally*", a maxim of sustainable engagement advocated by the UN and defended in the Statutes of AIP-IAP.

SCOPE AND PRINCIPLES

The "translation" of complex ideas into simple sentences is a lengthy process inherent to human behavior and other systems, governed by the *principle of minimum effort* and aimed at optimizing habits and resources. Linguistics, in its attempt to describe how languages evolve, function, and are used, seeks to minimize communicational noise, regardless of the form in which it is expressed.

Archer Taylor's ironic statement – that *an incommunicable quality allows us to distinguish when an expression is or is not proverbial* – constitutes a permanent challenge for researchers to continue searching for the definition of proverb. Among them, Wolfgang Mieder describes a proverb as "*a short phrase, generally known to the people, containing wisdom, truth, morals and traditional views in a metaphorical, fixed and memorable way, and which is transmitted from generation to generation*".

The following important aspects follow from this definition:

- Popular origin – signifying on the one hand the author's lack of knowledge and, on the other, validation by the collective;
- Short and fixed in nature – for easier memorization according to the principle of minimum effort and, simultaneously, to guarantee survival in transmission from generation to generation;
- Functionality – offering practical advice and alluding to moral truths consolidated in the wisdom acquired through daily experience;
- Universality – expressing the same reactions to concrete situations specific to the environmental experience of each culture.

The strategic vision of considering paremiology as a natural bridge between different heritages was expressed in the purposes enshrined in the AIP-IAP Statute, namely regarding the valorization of paremiological cultural heritage and its dissemination in cultural areas, encouraging international cooperation between academics and institutions working in related scientific fields. The establishment of educational programs aimed at transmitting

paremiological culture, and the organization of international conference cycles were also explicitly stated in the statutory purposes as a way of bringing peoples and cultures closer together.

AIP-IAP – a UNESCO-accredited NGO that provides consultancy services to the UNESCO Committee for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage in the area of oral tradition and which promotes the UNESCO Paremiology Club-Tavira (CUP-T) – contributes to the realization of the ideals and principles proclaimed by UNESCO, carrying out actions distributed across the following areas of intervention:

- a) schooling, this approach aims to leverage the educational potential of proverbs and similar expressions as an interdisciplinary strategy that fosters creativity;
- b) community, with intergenerational initiatives that foster socially active environments, extracurricular learning, and paremiological experiences among different target audiences.
- c) globalizing, in line with the ideals and principles proclaimed by UNESCO and oriented towards the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage, in the field of oral tradition – paremiology and related fields.

The joint action of AIP-IAP/CUP-T in these areas of intervention has enabled its acceptance as a guarantor in the defense and promotion of UNESCO's ideals through the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), namely SDGs 3, 4, 5, 14, 15, 16 and 17. This last goal is of enormous importance for the role that AIP-IAP plays in supporting and influencing the creation of strong SDG partnerships (Associations, Municipalities, Universities, among other Civil Society Institutions) to achieve the ambitious goals of the 2030 Agenda. Proverbs, as expressions of popular wisdom, are deeply rooted cultural instruments that play strategic roles in communication, creating empathy and collective mobilization.

JUSTIFICATION

Portugal is a country with characteristics that make it a valid interlocutor in broader socio-political and multicultural spaces, and therefore we cannot ignore the consequences of migratory phenomena. Whether considering migrant communities residing outside their territory of origin or those returning to it, several researchers point to communication problems and poor integration into the host community. Respect for the cultures present includes mutual recognition of differences, and the mutual desire for accommodation has justified the creation of language and culture courses that consider the *principle of minimum effort* from a perspective of optimizing habits and resources in a timely manner.

The use of proverbial expressions in educational practice is an added value both from the point of view of vocabulary learning and the cultural information necessary for understanding the cultures and heritages of the actors present.

The proposal for organizing the innovative P:PNEDP seminar aims to be a responsible exercise of the freedom to learn and teach from an active citizenship perspective, filling a gap in the curriculum in the areas of communication, education and human resource management.

TARGET AUDIENCE

Teacher training is a structural pillar of education, increasingly focused on the civic preparation of citizens knowledgeable in specific subjects and the appropriate approaches to transmitting that knowledge. However, in current times, it is important to include critical reflection on the subjects of the training curriculum. The proverbs "*To reap good fruits, first*

plant good roots" and "*Good students make good teachers*" suggest a symbiotic relationship that will benefit society in general and enhance the credibility of training institutions. The P:PNEDP seminar emerges at a time increasingly marked by interdependence, has an international scope, and is intended for:

- Cultural decision-makers from private and public institutions
- Local government recruitment and selection managers
- Civil society leaders responsible for territorial protection

AIMS

The training that the P:PNEDP seminar aims to provide is intended to:

- raise awareness among stakeholders at their different levels of action
- promote the implementation of measures for the effective integration of migrants
- increase learning of the language of the host country
- promote a balance between duties and rights in the defense of territories
- utilize the formative potential of proverbs as a bridge to social coexistence

Considering the heterogeneity of the target audience, both in terms of their prior preparation and the specific needs of each migrant, the seminar's structure takes the form of a *mosaic*, that is, it will incorporate lines of action and contributions from paremiology in areas related to the group's training.

For example::

Education	Health	Justice
Agriculture/Environment	P:PNEDP	Gastronomy
Arts/Technology	Climate	Tradition

The seminar's objectives are distributed across the cognitive, affective and relational domains, allowing participants to engage in active learning with a view to:

- acquire new attitudes and skills
- critically analyze concrete communication situations
- develop competencies as an information manager
- contribute to the acquisition of a general culture of peace
- reduce the distance between "*self*" and "*other*" as an affirmation of identity
- humanize the global village through the elevation of universal values
- identify essential aspects of one's own culture and other cultures
- promote the emergence of responsible attitudes of intervention
- translate real-life situations through proverbial expressions
- value one's own cultural self-growth.

PROGRAM/CONTENTS

The P:PNEDP seminar corresponds to a training unit for each of the areas indicated in the *mosaic*; each unit will have 2 sessions of 2 hours per month – the first, taught by a specialist in that area; the second, for discussion of the participants' work. In addition to the total of 36 hours

of training, there will be a final 2-hour session to evaluate the impact of the seminar on each participant's performance in their area of expertise.

Note: the program content for each training unit will be indicated by the respective specialist.

METODOLOGY

The methodology used in the P:PNEDP seminar is based on current technological communication facilities between trainer-participant-trainer, with each unit responsible for choosing the most appropriate means for the content being taught. A high level of commitment is required from the trainer to minimize noise arising from the way the material is presented, as well as to facilitate discussions among participants.

WHEN

The philosophy inherent in the P:PNEDP seminar calls for the timely preparation of the content of each unit and the self-learning skills of the participants. Responsible time management is recommended for both. For each unit, the local time of the trainer and the local time of the participants will need to be adjusted.

WHERE

The P:PNEDP seminar was designed to function without restrictions dictated by geographical location and can be followed in any location with available communication between trainer and participant.

MATERIAL

The materials used in the P:PNEDP seminar will be progressively made available in formats that make interactivity more effective. The use of multimedia documents and other resources available on the Internet will be recommended.

ASSESSMENT

The evaluation of participation in the P:PNEDP seminar presents the training modality carried out in the second session of each unit. The final evaluation will be carried out through an *essay* on the *impact of the seminar* on the participant's professional life, with special reference to the *importance of the unit* that contributed most to their development as a citizen.

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